

Development of chitosan encapsulated thyme essential oil as an alternative fruit fly repellent for household use

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Introduction and Background

Fruit flies are small seasonal pests that are attracted to, feed, and breed on fruits and vegetables. Fruit fly infestation cause unsightly scenes and pose health risk by passing foodborne germs. Seasonal fruit fly infestations, as an unwanted byproduct of food waste composting, has become a growing problem as more people compost food waste to reduce greenhouse gas emissions and landfills. Plant essential oils (EO) have been a source for commercial insect repellent sprays and products containing essential oils are widely used for pest control. However, these insect sprays are of short effect duration and are not suitable for indoor fruit fly infestation control because they are aerosols and can easily contaminate nearby foods. In this study, thyme oil was encapsulated in a chitosan matrix to create a fruit fly repellent that allows slow release for fruit fly infestation control purpose.

Compost bin as fruit fly breeding site

No breeding site with fruit fly repellent product

Results

Methodology

Optimization of Product Composition

	1% Chitosan	2% Chitosan	3% Chitosan
0.5% Thyme oil	26.3%±3.5%	44.2%±3.8%	69.8%±7.6%
1% Thyme oil	29.7%±3.0%	41.6%±4.7%	50.6%±5.1%
2% Thyme oil	24.8%±1.4%	45.8%±3.1%	38.7%±2.3%
3% Thyme oil	21.1%±0.9%	35.2%±3.4%	43.4%±4.1%

	1% Chitosan	2% Chitosan	3% Chitosan
0.5% Thyme oil	12.4%±1.6%	10.4%±0.9%	10.9%±1.2%
1% Thyme oil	27.9%±2.8%	19.6%±2.2%	15.9%±1.6%
2% Thyme oil	46.6%±2.7%	43.1%±3.0%	24.3%±1.4%
3% Thyme oil	59.5%±2.7%	49.7%±4.8%	40.8%±3.8%

Composition and Yield of the Prototype

Composition			Yield	
Chitosan concentration	Thyme oil concentration	Tween 80 concentration	Encapsulation efficiency	Loading capacity
2%	2%	1%	65.1±3.5%	61.2±3.3%

Preserved Thyme Oil Content and Effect Over Time

Thyme oil content (ul / 10 mg)	Fresh	Week 1	Week 2	Week 4	Week 6
Thyme oil content	2.90±0.08	2.85±0.27	2.99±0.27	2.89±0.16	2.98±0.15
Repelling effect	100%	100%	100%	100%	100%

Image of product

Future Work

Further studies will be conducted to determine the long-term stability of the prototype. Additionally, although the current product showed 100% fruit fly repelling efficiency, eggs and larvae already existing in the compost bin may still develop into adult flies, and it is unclear if the product will kill eggs and larvae. A future study is to set up assays to examine if the product can prevent egg and larvae from developing into adult flies. Assays for more encapsulating materials (e.g., other natural polymers such as agar, gelatin, and alginate) will be investigated to determine the optimal encapsulation for fruit fly repelling efficiency.

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